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*** "A DIFFERENT LOOK AT POLICY MAKERS"
BEFORE AND AFTER IMPLEMENTATION
POLARIZATIONS**

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POLICY MAKERS BEFORE AND AFTER IMPLEMENTATION

A DIFFERENT LOOK AT THE POLARIZATIONS

**A DIFFERENT LOOK AT POLICY MAKERS' BEFORE AND AFTER
IMPLEMENTATION POLARIZATIONS**

Self

Carrying out a systematic investigation of the key mechanisms driving elite polarization in world states, using a general model of the dynamics of ideas, is important for literature and because it is a subject to be explored. It is not difficult to see that the self-reinforcing nature of elite processes can explain this polarization with voter preferences constituting its asymmetrical structure.

The subject that needs to be analyzed is the effects of the second and third world countries due to the politics reflected from the great and powerful states and the policies that cause this. For this reason, the difference in practice and the fact that even the supervision of the legality of the policies carried out by the elected is dependent on the parliament is important for this reason. Therefore, the relevant research, analysis and compilation of information in the literature makes a difference in order to explain the subject from a different perspective and to open the door to wider research, albeit a little. The frequency of studies suggesting that subtle differences in the frequency and size of public opinion shifts to the left and right over time may have a differential impact on the self-reinforcing processes of elites, causing Republicans to polarize faster than Democrats, compelled this research. We see polarization accelerating as self-empowerment approaches a critical threshold. Republicans seem to have crossed that threshold, while Democrats are now approaching it.

This study examines the causes and consequences of polarization, especially in the matters we have mentioned. examines politics and its effects on politics.

Keywords: *Policy makers, Polarization in Politics, Political Polarization, Contradictions of Political Polarization*

abstract

Conducting a systematic investigation of the key mechanisms driving elite polarization in world states, using a general model of dynamics of opinion, is important in terms of literature and as a subject to be explored. It is not difficult to see that the self-reinforcing nature of elite processes can explain this polarization with voter preferences being its asymmetrical structure. The subject that needs to be analyzed is the effects of the second and third world countries due to the politics reflected from the great and powerful states and the policies that cause this.

For this reason, the difference in practice and the naturalness of the fact that even the supervision of the legality of the policies carried out by the elected is dependent on the parliament is important for this reason. Therefore, the relevant research, analysis and compilation of the information in the literature make a difference in order to explain the subject from a different perspective and to open the door to wider research, albeit a little. The frequency of studies suggesting that subtle differences in the frequency and size of public opinion shifts to the left and right over time may have a differential impact on the self-reinforcing processes of elites, causing Republicans to polarize faster than Democrats, compelled this research. We see polarization accelerating as self-empowerment approaches a critical threshold. Republicans seem to have crossed that threshold, while Democrats are now approaching it.

This study examines the effects of the causes and consequences of polarization, especially on the issues we have mentioned, on the administration, politics and policies.

Keywords: *Policy makers, Political Polarization, Political Polarization, Political Polarization Con traditions*

1. Introduction

It would be fair to say that there are two different dimensions to informal political communication:

- 1) *the degree of coincidental similarity in non-political characteristics;*
- and 2) *standing agreements on a contentious political issue.*

Regardless of their political affiliation, the results of the literature review with both moderate and strong views show that support for redistribution is increasing and polarization is decreasing. The available analysis data (collaborative analysis of literature outputs based on detailed reviews) also reveals an asymmetry¹ about the effects of accidental similarity and shared identity on affect:

The studies extend to the field of political change of opinion, bringing the results to real-world implications for the (re)design of social media platforms. The decision of many individuals to choose to keep politics out of their social networks encourages cross-cutting political communication based on non-political commonalities. In terms, it is a potential solution to foster consensus on potentially divisive and partisan issues.

2. Polarization Data by Information on Media Platforms

Content on the main timeline of many social media platforms is selected and sorted by personalization algorithms. By consistently ranking certain content higher, these algorithms can strengthen some messages while reducing the visibility of others. There is intense public and scholarly debate about the possibility that some political groups might benefit more from algorithmic amplification than others. In six, the mainstream political right was identified as having higher "Algorithmic amplification" than the mainstream political left.

¹ Interaction with opposing individuals greatly reduces feelings of intimacy and this is considered normal; however, interacting with individuals with coherent views leaves them only moderate.

² Quantitative evidence from a long-running, large-scale randomized experiment that linked a random control group of approximately 2 million active accounts per day to a reverse-chronological content stream without algorithmic personalization on a popular social media platform alone. available.

3. Different Manifestations of Polarization

In the last decade, polarization on various issues has increased in many Western democracies, leading to different beliefs, preferences and behaviors in societies.

A model has been developed and used in many scientific methods to explore the effects of polarization on the probability of a society to coordinate on welfare-enhancing action in a context where the collective benefits are achieved only if enough individuals take the action. Studying the effects of different manifestations of polarization has been made possible by these methods:

- *the heterogeneity of preferences,*
- the separation of the social network,*
- and • *the interaction between the two.*

In this context, heterogeneity has the ability to capture perceived benefits as distinct from coordination, which can lead to different intentions and sensitivity to the intentions of others. Since individuals can base their decisions only on their immediate neighbors, the separation of the social network can create a bottleneck in the flows of information about others' preferences. In addition, heterogeneous preferences may be evenly distributed among the population or clustered in the local network that reflects or systematically diverges from the views of the wider society.

4. Ideological Polarization

Extreme polarization can undermine democracy by making reconciliation impossible and turning politics into a zero-sum game, with the sometimes unexpected effects of the results. "Ideological "Polarization" (the degree to which political views are widely dispersed) is already a strong interaction among the elite, but less powerful among the general public (N. McCarty, *Polarization: What Everyone Should Know*, 2019, pp. 50–68). For example, strong mutual distrust and hostility between Democrats and Republicans in developed countries, combined with the already strong ideological polarization of elites, can lead to increased ideological polarization among the population. Two questions are important here:

- 1) *Is there a level of ideological polarization on which polarization feeds into itself to become an out-of-control process?*
- 2) *If so, what policy interventions can prevent such dangerous positive feedback loops?*³

To explore these questions, interactions occur with the propensity of two actors to interact ("exposure").

³ S. Klar, Y. Krupnikov, JB Ryan, Emotional Polarization or Partisan Contempt? Resolving a Discontent for the Opposite Party Who Dislikes Partisanship. *Public opinion*. P.82, 379-390 (2018).

It is of course necessary to distinguish between how they react when However, it would be correct to propose an agent-based ideological polarization model, which argues that interaction between similar actors reduces their differences, while interaction reduces the difference between them. This will increase the differences between different actors.

According to the analysis, different levels of tolerance towards other views also need to be addressed.

Responding to other viewpoints are important, effective and comparatively needed as well as exploring the effects of exposure to different actors on the polarization of multiple ideological dimensions, economic self-interest, and external shocks. The results suggest strategies to prevent or at least slow the development of extreme polarization.

5. Uncoordinated Responses

The international network of environmental agreements (IEA) cares about certain criteria depending on the changes in the conditions addressed by the nation-states certain agreements. It is normal for their uncoordinated responses to be characterized as a complex adaptive system (CAS) in which it can produce apparently coordinated patterns of behavior at the system level. Unfortunately, it is not currently possible to apply a CAS approach, as the rules governing national interventions are not fully understood. The polarization of both political parties and voters is leading, therefore, to a secular decline in national loyalty to some IEAs. Accordingly, the causal mechanisms are not clear. In line with the aim of our article, it is necessary to clarify the effect of polarization on the rules that underpin national responses . Yet the analysis and data lead the conclusion along the lines of the need to understand the effects of such conditioning on the rules governing national interventions.

Political theorists have long argued that informal political debate is essential to the maintenance of democracy.

The following two perspectives provide further detail on their belief that it plays an important role:⁵

- *It is thought that civil and respectful exchanges on controversial issues among individuals with different perspectives not only increase trust in democracy, but also improve the understanding of self and others.*⁶

⁴ Whether the national commitment will be strengthened due to the increase in national obligations is not polarized per se. Much depends on the criteria and reasons for the change in national obligations.

⁵ CA Bail et al, Exposure to opposing views on social media can increase political polarization. Proc. natl. Acad. Science US 115, 9216–9221 (2018).

⁶ I. Himelboim, S. McCreery, M. Smith, Birds of a Tweet: Network and Twitter to Examine Cross-Ideological Exposure Integrating Content Analytics. J. Computer Mediated Communication. 18, 154-174 (2013).

- Unfortunately, the assumed benefits of political exchanges⁷ based on the developed countries of the world in general, especially when they anticipate conflict^{8 9} *It is limited to the observation that they tend to avoid political discussions.*¹⁰
- Also, when people are exposed to the political views of strangers “in the wild,” as on social media platforms, discussions often turn into rudeness and thus increase rather than lessen polarization.

6. Incidental Political Arguments

A possible solution to polarized and causal debates has been inspired by recent studies of “accidental” political debates between individuals who are already friends.¹¹ Since friendship networks display a greater diversity of political views than is apparent even for their members, these fortuitous conversations expose their interlocutors to different points of view. has a quitting effect. While promising to reduce polarization, an important limitation of incidental political debates is that there are networks of friendship, even if they are more heterogeneous in terms of political views than people realize. As we want to present and summarize in the main idea in our article, we show that building on the idea that coincidental similarities between interlocutors can reduce polarization of opinion in a large-scale, pre-recorded experiment, with reference to articles written in other literature whose similarity varies across two dimensions, points to normal and expected results.

Consequently, differences in their stance on a “focal” political issue, such as government policies regarding wealth redistribution and a range of demographic and biographical characteristics such as age, gender, hometown, university, sports teams, personal interests, and idiosyncratic quirks, differs.

Diversity, also in terms of similarity according to personal characteristics, will of course result in the systematic matching of people, the result of our experiment capturing a key mechanism underlying the effectiveness of chance conversations, namely conversations taking place between individuals who share non-political experiences, preferences, and qualities.

⁷ P.J. Hasson, Manipulators: Facebook, Google, Twitter and Big Tech's Battle for the Conservatives (Regnery, 2020).

⁸ P. Barberá, J.T. Jost, J. Nagler, J.A. Tucker, R. Bonneau, Tweeting Left to Right: Online Political Communication An Echo Room More Than Just? *Psycho. Science* 26, 1531–1542 (2015).

⁹ O'callaghan, D. Greene, M. Conway, J. Carthy, P. Cunningham, Down The (White) Rabbit Hole: The Far Right and Online Recommendation Systems.

¹⁰ T. Gillespie, The politics of 'platforms'. *New Media Soc.* 12, 347–364 (2010).

^{11th} According to the random model, friendship networks often arise from some combination of shared social contexts (for example, school, work, or church) and mutual friendships, both of which are not overtly political in nature. Conversations in these networks are therefore mostly apolitical, but sometimes accidentally straying into politics.

7. An Example Based on the Importance of Social Media

Political content appears to be an important part of public speaking for any popular platform on social media. Politicians, political organizations and news organizations interact with large audiences on any popular platform on social media. At the same time, any of the popular platforms in this mentioned social media, algorithms that learn from data are used to rank the content on the platform. This interplay of algorithmic content curation and political discourse has been the subject of intense scholarly debate and public scrutiny. Any popular social media platform, when first set up as a service, would offer individuals the content of the accounts they follow, arranged in a reverse chronological stream. Now that they are based on algorithms, individuals also see old posts that are thought to be relevant to them along with accounts they do not follow directly.

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

It has some inherent limitations in evaluating data on polarization. The first limitation comes from interaction effects between individuals. Thus, when faced with shared content in social networks, results from inference from randomized controlled experiments show that, despite efforts to avoid polarization, the causal quantities of interest do not provide unbiased estimates.

Based on this, complex causal inference is often used to approximate causal quantities, as it will not guarantee unbiased estimations in the complex environment of the main timeline algorithm, especially in terms of the results of any popular platform in social media, where the latest literature alternative research results depending on today's technology and uses can be obtained. Choosing not to use its mechanisms is counterproductive.

It is therefore beyond the scope of most studies to construct a detailed causal diagram of this complex system. That is, the statistics reported alongside peer effects on polarization likely underestimate the true causal effects of personalization. This requires that the difference between polarization, polarization and relations be well understood by the determinants of the political mechanism and used well on the masses of the people.

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